

BALLADA JANRIDA DRAMATIZM

Bolliyeva Madina

ADU Tayanch doktoranti.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ballada janrining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, xususan, undagi drammatizm, konflikt va fojaviylik masalalari tadqiq etilgan. Muallif ballada dunyosidagi inson va taqdir o'rtasidagi ontologik ziddiyatlar, vaziyatning drammatizmini kuchaytiruvchi dialoglar hamda Tabiat obrazining harakatlanuvchi personaj sifatidagi rolini nazariy jihatdan asoslab beradi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy she'riyatda drammatizmning mistik unsurlar orqali emas, balki nostalgik sog'inch, inson hayotining o'tkinchiligi va yolg'izlik tuyg'ulari orqali aks etishi ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ballada, drammatizm, konflikt, syujet, kompozitsiya, kulminatsiya, Abdulla Sher, lirik qahramon, ramziy obraz, yolg'izlik.

DRAMATISM IN THE BALLAD GENRE

Annotation. This article examines the specific features of the ballad genre, in particular, the issues of drama, conflict, and tragedy in it. The author theoretically substantiates the ontological contradictions between man and fate in the ballad world, dialogues that enhance the drama of the situation, and the role of the image of Nature as a moving character. It is also shown that drama in modern poetry is reflected not through mystical elements, but through nostalgic longing, the transience of human life, and feelings of loneliness.

Keywords: ballad, drama, conflict, plot, composition, culmination, Abdulla Sher, lyrical hero, symbolic image, loneliness.

One of the basic definitions of a ballad is that it has a tragic resolution to a personal, domestic, family conflict. In a ballad, the emotional experiences of the lyrical hero are determined by the conflict he has with the external world (or social environment) in which he is surrounded and with himself. "In the conflict, the lyrical hero is often opposed by fate, destiny, and the forces of eternal dominion, or by certain negative characters (evil sorcerers, hostile forces). The ontological conflict of man and fate serves as a constant plot center"¹.

In modern Uzbek ballads, we can also see the conflicts of the heroes with each other or with external forces. For example, in A. Sher's "Ballad about the East", the conflicts of the young man in love with the external environment and the girl's father are described.

"In the world of the ballad, there is a tragic sympathy and the eternal impossibility of changing the wheel of events, and the heroes constantly maintain balance in a state of trials and doom (border) to destruction".

"In classical and folk ballads, dialogues (conversations) and various forms of increasing repetitions are actively used to enhance the drama of the situation and bring the tragic resolution closer. The replicas in the dialogues are built on the principle of a "growing chain of questions and answers", sometimes alternating between representatives of "this world" and "that world"².

¹ Кавылин А.Г. Русская народная баллада. – Москва, 2003.

² Осьмухина О.Ю. Баллада в современной отечественной поэзии. – Москва, 2019.

A group of ballads tells about the lives of folk heroes, often ending with their death. Or they end with the tragedy of the heroes' disappointed feelings.

“In romantic and lyrical ballads, drama is often enhanced by the image of Nature. Nature is not just a background, but takes on the role of a moving character: it reflects the feelings and tragedy of the hero, and sometimes performs the function of revenge (the inevitability of punishment) or accusation, manifesting itself in such terrible elements as thunder, storm, whirlpool”.

“In contemporary poetry (in the work of the “traditionalists”), drama and tension are created not through mystical elements, but through the transience and irreversibility of human life, nostalgic longing for the past, the loss of ties with the past, and feelings of loneliness and discomfort in the present”³.

Today, one of the poets who continues the tradition of writing ballads of the poets of the last century is Abdulla Sher. The poet's ballads structurally correspond to the requirements of the genre. His ballads served to enrich the genre with their thematic and ideological diversity. In the poet's “Ballad about a Cold Man”, we see a nostalgic image of a life that is based on a small incident.

Tashqarida qish kezar mag‘ur,
Izg‘irinda kukunlanar qor.
Derazadan tushib turgan nur
Bamisoli bir quchoq bahor.

Yo‘l chetidan sovqotgan odam
Tikiladi kelib havasi:
Ichkarida issiq, yosh olam –
Er-xotinning baxtli davrasi.

Tikilaru bir muddat, so‘ngra,
Birdan tiz cho‘kardi u qorga.
Va boladek o‘kinib, ho‘ngrab
Ko‘z-yoshini to‘kardi qorga.

Deraza-chi, sochganicha nur
Ko‘z-ko‘z qilar oila taftin.
Yolg‘iz odam esa behuzur
Yuzga bosar ikkala kaftin.

So‘ng, dovdirab ketar u behol
Dala bo‘ylab, unutib yo‘lni.
Tortqilaydi beshafqat shamol
Ho‘l yuzlarni berkitgan qo‘lni.

³ Савмухий Г.А. Мифическое начало баллада. – Москва, 2019.

The ballad has a compact composition. The work consists of exposition, development, climax, and resolution. The winter landscape and the light from the window serve as exposition.

The story begins with the frozen man gazing longingly at the happy family. His kneeling in the snow and crying is the climax. At the end, his helpless departure across the field creates a dramatic resolution.

The plot is built on the basis of external and internal conflict. The external conflict is the contrast between the cold winter and the warm room. The internal conflict is related to the lonely person's need for love and happiness. The hero, seeing the scene of a happy family, feels his spiritual emptiness even more deeply.

The ballad features real and symbolic images. The cold man is the central lyrical-dramatic image, expressing loneliness, thirst for love, and the subtle feelings of the human soul. The image of a couple is a symbol of family happiness, kindness, and warmth.

The symbolic images of winter and wind are symbols of the cruelty of life and the difficulties of human destiny, while the Light and the warm room are images of hope, happiness, and spiritual comfort.

In conclusion, the ballad effectively illuminates the spiritual loneliness of man and his need for love. The harmony between the external landscape and the inner experience is given in the work with high artistic skill. In addition, allegories, the contrast of the seasons, and symbolic images are widely used in describing the plot.

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